

Cyber security and management of digital collections in academic libraries in Cross River State

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Abstract

Background: This study investigated the contribution of cybersecurity measures to the management of digital collections in academic libraries within Cross River State, Nigeria. With the increasing digitization of library resources, understanding how cybersecurity components such as data integrity, access control, user authentication, and encryption support digital collection management has become essential.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey research design was adopted, involving 42 library staff from the University of Calabar and the University of Cross River State. Data were collected using the *Cybersecurity and Digital Collections in Academic Libraries Scale (CSDCALS)*, a researcher-developed instrument validated through Item-Content Validity Index (I-CVI) and Scale Content Validity Index (S-CVI), and found reliable using Cronbach's alpha. Simple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses and analyze responses to the research questions.

Findings/Results: The results revealed that data integrity, access control, user authentication, and encryption significantly influence the effective management of digital collections in academic libraries. These cybersecurity components were found to enhance the accuracy, security, and reliability of digital resources.

Implications: The findings underscore the importance of integrating cybersecurity strategies into digital library practices to safeguard information assets and ensure consistent access to high-quality digital content. Failure to address these components may compromise the integrity and availability of digital collections.

Conclusion: Cybersecurity plays a pivotal role in the management of digital collections in academic libraries. Its components contribute meaningfully to preserving the integrity and accessibility of digital resources.

Recommendations: Academic libraries should adopt robust data integrity protocols, including regular data audits, the use of checksums, and implementation of version control systems. Additionally, strengthening access control, user authentication, and encryption mechanisms will further protect digital collections and enhance user trust in digital library services.

Keywords: Cyber security, data integrity, access control, users' authentication, encryption, digital collections, and academic libraries

Introduction

The management of digital collections in academic libraries is a crucial aspect of modern librarianship, reflecting the evolving landscape of information access and preservation. As digital resources become increasingly integral to academic research, libraries must adopt effective strategies for managing these collections to ensure their accessibility, usability, and long-term preservation. Digital collections encompass a wide range of materials, including e-books, journals, databases, multimedia files, and institutional repositories, all of which require specialised management practices. Academic libraries play a pivotal role in supporting academic and scholarly activities by providing access to diverse digital collections. According to Lippincott (2020), the shift towards digital resources necessitates a comprehensive approach to collection management, encompassing acquisition, cataloguing, metadata creation, and digital preservation. Effective digital collection management not only facilitates seamless

access to information but also enhances the discoverability and use of these resources by researchers and students.

Academic libraries in the digital era are marred with so many challenges. One of the primary challenges in managing digital collections is ensuring long-term accessibility and preservation. Digital preservation strategies are essential to safeguard digital content against technological obsolescence, data corruption, and other risks. As noted by Conway (2021), libraries must implement robust preservation frameworks, including regular data backups, format migration, and the use of digital preservation standards and protocols. Moreover, the integration of digital collections into library services requires effective metadata management. Metadata, which provides descriptive, structural, and administrative information about digital resources, is crucial for organising and retrieving digital content. As argued by Gorman (2022), accurate and comprehensive metadata enhances the discoverability of digital collections and supports interoperability between different information systems. User experience is another critical consideration in the management of digital collections. Libraries must ensure that digital resources are accessible through user-friendly interfaces and platforms. This involves optimising search functionalities, providing clear navigation paths, and ensuring that digital content is compatible with various devices and software. According to Smith and Kamal (2020), improving user experience in accessing digital collections can significantly increase user engagement and satisfaction. Similarly, the rapid advancement of technology also presents opportunities for enhancing digital collection management. Emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) can be leveraged to automate metadata creation, improve content recommendation systems, and enhance digital preservation efforts. As highlighted by Wang et al. (2021), AI and ML can transform digital collection management by enabling more efficient and effective processes. However, cyber security has not been considered as a factor in the issues plaguing

The management of digital collections in academic libraries has been the subject of extensive empirical research, addressing various aspects such as acquisition, preservation, user access, and metadata management. For example, a study by Chen et al. (2021) explored the strategies employed by academic libraries in China

to manage digital collections. The research found that the integration of cloud-based solutions significantly improved the efficiency of digital resource management. Libraries that adopted cloud storage and services reported enhanced accessibility, scalability, and cost-effectiveness. Additionally, the study highlighted the importance of training library staff in using these technologies to maximise their potential, in line with the assertion of Edam-Agbor et al. (2025) that librarians exhibit a high level of awareness, acceptance, and application artificial intelligence in research libraries.

In addition, a survey conducted by Jones and Smith (2020) in North American universities revealed that the implementation of robust digital preservation frameworks was a key factor in ensuring the longevity of digital collections. The study emphasised the use of open-source digital preservation tools such as LOCKSS (Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe) and Archivematica, which provide comprehensive solutions for preserving digital content against technological obsolescence and data corruption. Another study was carried out by Patel and Roy (2022) on the metadata practices in European research libraries. The study found that libraries employing standardised metadata schemas such as Dublin Core and MODS (Metadata Object Description Schema) achieved higher levels of discoverability and interoperability of their digital collections. Wang et al.'s (2022) study found that user-friendly design, intuitive navigation, and advanced search functionalities were crucial for enhancing user satisfaction and engagement. The study also recommended incorporating user feedback into the design process to tailor digital library services to meet the specific needs of the user community. Other studies have corroborated that digital rights management, digital literacy training programmes; digital content acquisition (Brown & Miller, 2020; Lee & Chen, 2021; Martinez & Lopez, 2020; Kaur & Singh, 2023) are essential in the management of digital collections in research libraries. However, specific attention on cybersecurity has not been focused on. Similarly, these studies with insightful findings were not carried out in this area. Context is important to avoid hasty generalisation. It is imperative, therefore, to examine the impact of cybersecurity on the management of digital collections in academic libraries in Cross River State.

Cyber security is integral to the effective management of digital collections in research libraries. Ensuring the security of digital resources involves a range of measures designed to protect data from unauthorised access, corruption, and loss. The relationship between cybersecurity and digital collection management can be understood through the following sub-variables. Data integrity means maintaining its accuracy and completeness over its lifecycle. Cybersecurity measures such as checksums, hashing, and regular integrity checks are essential to protect digital collections from corruption and unauthorised alterations. Maintaining data integrity ensures that researchers can trust the authenticity and reliability of the resources they access (Smith & Johnson, 2021). **Access control** mechanisms are crucial in preventing unauthorised access to digital collections. This involves defining who can access certain data and what actions they can perform. Access control policies and technologies such as role-based access control (RBAC) and multi-factor authentication (MFA) help ensure that only authorised users can view or modify digital collections, thereby protecting sensitive information and preserving intellectual property rights (Brown et al., 2022).

User authentication is essential to verify the identities of users accessing digital collections. Libraries often use a combination of username/password pairs, biometric authentication, and smart cards to ensure secure access. Ensuring robust authentication helps prevent unauthorised access and protects the integrity and confidentiality of digital resources (Garcia & Martinez, 2022). Encryption is a key technique for protecting data both in transit and at rest. By encrypting digital collections, libraries can ensure that even if data is intercepted or accessed by unauthorised users, it remains unreadable and secure. This is particularly important for sensitive research data that requires high levels of confidentiality (Patel & Kumar, 2020). Therefore, cybersecurity is essential for the effective management of digital collections in academic libraries. It encompasses a wide range of practices and technologies designed to protect data integrity, ensure proper access control, detect and respond to threats, authenticate users, encrypt data, back up and recover data, train staff, and comply with legal requirements. By integrating robust cybersecurity measures into their digital collection management strategies, libraries can safeguard their digital resources, ensure their long-term

preservation, and provide secure and reliable access to researchers and users. Hence, the following research questions were raised.

Research questions

1. What is the contribution of data integrity to the management of digital collections in academic libraries?
2. What is the contribution of access control to the management of digital collections in academic libraries?
3. What is the contribution of user authentication to the management of digital collections in academic libraries?
4. What is the contribution of encryption to the management of digital collections in academic libraries?

Methodology

The research was conducted in Cross River State, located in the South-South region of Nigeria. It is known for its educational institutions, including the University of Calabar and the University of Cross River State. These institutions host academic libraries that support research and learning. The state provides a relevant context for studying cybersecurity in digital library collections. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design to select a total of 42 library staff in the study area which is 50% of the total population of the study made up of 84 library staff. The adoption of the design was to ensure that information from different groups of respondents was obtained at the same time using a questionnaire to obtain responses. The sample of the study was collected using cluster sampling techniques. In the three clusters (University of Calabar, University of Cross River and University of Education) in the study area, 50% was used to select the respondents from every cluster.

The instrument used for the study was a questionnaire titled 'Cyber Security and Digital Collections in Academic Libraries Scale' (CSDCALS). The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A focused on demographic information such as gender, professional status, and year of experience. Section B was made up of

five variables designed to measure the variables of the independent and dependent variables, such as data integrity, access control, user authentication, encryption, and management of digital collections in academic libraries. The section was made up of 30 items, with 5 items each measuring the sub-variables of the independent variable, while 10 items were used in measuring the dependent variables. The items were measured using a numeric scale in the pattern of the Likert format. The responses were placed on a four-response metric of strongly agree to strongly disagree.

The content and construct validity of the scales were established using a quantitative approach. Both instruments, the Cyber Security Scale (CSS) and the 'Digital Collections in Academic Libraries Questionnaire' (DCALQ), were subjected first to face and content validation. This was done using nine experts drawn from three professional areas: educational technology (n = 4), library and information science (n = 3), and measurement and evaluation (n = 2). Each was given a role to play in the validation process. The quantitative approach to content validity was carried out using the Item-Content Validity Indices (I-CVI) and Scale Content Validity Indices (S-CVI) as recommended by different scholars (Yusoff, 2019). For the Cyber Security Scale (CSS), the I-CVI for data integrity ranged from 0.78 to 0.89; for access control, 0.75 to 0.90; and for user authentication, 0.79 to 0.95, and encryption has the values of 0.78-0.88. Similarly, the scale-content validity indices (S-CVI) ranged from 0.88 to 0.95. The average proportion of items considered relevant for the three scales was 0.89. This implies that, on aggregate, 89.0% of the validators considered that the items in the CSS were relevant for the study. This range of values obtained was sufficient to establish content validity for the CSS (see Lynn, 1986; Yusof, 2019). The same was done for the DCRLQ; the item-content validity indices for the digital collection of resources ranged from 0.77 to 0.87. The scale-content validity indices (SCVI) for the DCRLQ ranged from 0.88 to 0.94. The average proportion of items considered relevant for the three scales was 0.85. This implies that, on aggregate, 85.0% of the validators considered that the items in the DCRLQ were relevant for the study.

A pilot study was further carried out to determine the reliability of the two scales, CCS and DCRLQ. The instrument was made up of 30 items that measured both

constructs. Was administered to 20 who were not part of the study. The data collected were analysed using Cronbach's alpha, and the result showed that the coefficient of the subscale ranged from 0.78 to 0.88, which is an indication that the instrument has internal stability. The data was collected by the researchers in various universities that were earmarked for the study. The researchers ensured ethical compliance by informing the respondents of the purpose of the study and what the data provided will be used for, as well as the security of their data. In this way, their consents were obtained; a total of 42 responses were obtained at the end of the administration. Data collected were analysed using simple regression statistic, and the result was presented appropriately.

Results and Discussion of the Findings

Hypothesis one

The result for hypothesis one, which stated that data does not contribute to the management of digital collections in academic libraries among staff, was presented in Table 1. The result in Table 1 revealed that $R = .601$, which implies that an increase in data integrity increases the management of digital collections in research libraries. A further look at the result showed that $Adj R^2 = .358$, which implies that the variance in management of digital collections in academic libraries could be attributed to the 35.8% contribution of data integrity of the staff. This implies that there are other factors that can contribute 64.2% to explaining the management of digital collections in research libraries. To test the hypothesis, the inferential statistic result was assessed, and the result as presented in Table 1 revealed that ($F=56.77, p<.001$). Since $p<.000$ is less than $p<.05$, this implies that hypothesis one, which stated that staff data integrity does not significantly influence management of digital collections in academic libraries in universities, was rejected and the alternate hypothesis supported.

Table 1: Simple regression analysis of the contribution of data integrity to the management of digital collections in academic libraries

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between	654.01	1	654.01		
Within	1889.64	39	11.52	56.77	.000
Total	1543.65	40			

*R=.601, R²=.361, Adj R²=.358, Std error=2.892, SS=Sum of squares, MS=Mean squares, df=degree of freedom, *=significant at 0.5 level*

Hypothesis two

The result for the hypothesis, which stated that access control does not contribute to the management of digital collections in academic libraries among staff, was presented in Table 2. The result in Table 2 revealed that $R = .865$, which implies that an increase in access control increases the management of digital collections in academic libraries. A further look at the result showed that $Adj R^2 = .744$, which implies that the variance in management of digital collections in academic libraries could be attributed to the 74.4% contribution of access control of the staff. This implies that there are other factors that can contribute 25.6% to explaining the management of digital collections in academic libraries. To test the hypothesis, the inferential statistic result was assessed, and the result as presented in Table 2 revealed that $F=80.79$, $p<.001$. Since $p<.000$ is less than $p<.05$, this implies that hypothesis two, which stated that staff data integrity does not significantly influence management of digital collections in academic libraries in universities, was rejected and the alternate hypothesis supported.

Table 2: Simple linear regression analysis of the contribution of data integrity to the management of digital collections in academic libraries

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between	297.60	1	297.60		
Within	1246.05	39	11.11	80.79	.000
Total	1543.65	40			

*R=.865, R² = .748, Adj R² =.744, Std error=1.543, SS=Sum of squares, MS=Mean squares, df=degree of freedom, *=significant at 0.5 level*

Hypothesis three

The result for hypothesis three, which stated that user authentication does not contribute to the management of digital collections in academic libraries among staff, was presented in Table 3. The result in Table 3 revealed that $R = .678$, which implies that an increase in user authentication increases management of digital collections in academic libraries. A further look at the result showed that $Adj R^2 = .450$, which implies that the variance in management of digital collections in academic libraries could be attributed to the 45.0% contribution of user authentication of the staff. This implies that there are other factors that can contribute 55.0% to explaining the management of digital collections in academic libraries. To test the hypothesis, the inferential statistic result was assessed, and the result as presented in Table 3 revealed that ($F=66.49, p<.001$), Since $p(.000)$ is less than $p(.05)$, this implies that hypothesis three, which stated that user authentication does not significantly influence management of digital collections in academic libraries in universities, was rejected and the alternate hypothesis supported.

Table 3: Simple linear regression analysis of the contribution of user authentication to the management of digital collections in academic libraries

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	f-val	p-val
Between	754.09	1	754.09		
Within	6789.56	598	11.35	66.49	.000
Total	7543.65	599			

*R=.678, R² = .459, Adj R² =.450, Std error=2.012, SS=Sum of squares, MS=Mean squares, df=degree of freedom, *=significant at 0.5 level*

Hypothesis four

The result for hypothesis one, which stated encryption does not contribute to management of digital collections in academic libraries among staff, was presented in Table 4. The result in Table 4 revealed that $R = .705$, which implies that an increase in encryption increases the management of digital collections in academic libraries. A further look at the result showed that $Adj R^2 = .491$, which implies that the variance in management of digital collections in academic libraries could be attributed to the 49.1% contribution of encryption of systems. This implies that there are other factors that can contribute 50.9% to explaining the management of digital collections in academic libraries. To test the hypothesis, the inferential statistic result was assessed, and the result as presented in Table 4 revealed that ($F=80.97^*$, $p<.001$). Since $p<.000$ is less than $p<.05$, this implies that hypothesis four, which stated encryption does not significantly influence management of digital collections in academic libraries in universities, was rejected and the alternate hypothesis supported.

Table 4: Simple linear regression analysis of the contribution of encryption to the management of digital collections in academic libraries

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between	299.65	1	299.65		
Within	1244.00	39	11.1	80.97	.000
Total	7543.65	40			

*R=.705, R² = .497, Adj R² =.491, Std error=2.232, SS=Sum of squares, MS=Mean squares, df=degree of freedom, *=significant at 0.5 level*

Discussion of finding

The study underscores the pivotal role of data integrity in the management of digital collections within academic libraries. Data integrity ensures that digital materials are accurate, complete, and reliable, which is essential for preserving their authenticity and usability over time. Academic libraries, tasked with curating vast amounts of digital content ranging from scholarly articles to historical archives, rely on data integrity to maintain the trustworthiness and scholarly value of their collections. The rationale for this study outcome lies in the foundational principles of information management and preservation. Data integrity safeguards against data corruption, unauthorised alterations, and loss, which are critical risks in digital environments (Thibodeau, 2015; Waters, Garrett, & Maron, 2019). By upholding data integrity standards, research libraries can mitigate these risks and ensure that digital collections remain accessible and reliable for future research and educational purposes.

Previous studies support the significance of data integrity in managing digital collections by highlighting its impact on collection sustainability and user trust. Thibodeau (2015) discusses the importance of robust data management practices in digital preservation initiatives, emphasising the role of data integrity in maintaining content authenticity and usability. Waters, Garrett, and Maron (2019) explore the challenges of data stewardship in research libraries, advocating for comprehensive strategies that prioritise data integrity to support long-term access and preservation goals. Furthermore, adherence to data integrity principles aligns

with professional standards and best practices in library and information science, emphasizing the ethical responsibility of libraries to preserve and provide access to trustworthy information (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 2015; Association of Research Libraries, 2012). By implementing effective data integrity measures, research libraries demonstrate their commitment to scholarly excellence, intellectual stewardship, and the advancement of knowledge in the digital age.

The study emphasises that access control is pivotal in managing digital collections within academic libraries. Access control refers to the mechanisms and policies that regulate who can access, modify, or use digital materials stored in library collections. This is crucial for safeguarding sensitive or copyrighted content, ensuring data security, and maintaining the integrity and authenticity of digital collections over time. The rationale for this study outcome lies in the necessity to balance open access with protection of intellectual property rights and privacy concerns in digital environments (Jones & Lauriault, 2017; Orim, Edam-Agbor & Olaniyi, 2019; Stvilia et al., 2017). Effective access control mechanisms enable research libraries to implement tailored access policies that align with legal requirements, ethical guidelines, and user needs, thereby enhancing the usability and trustworthiness of their digital collections.

Previous studies support the importance of access control in managing digital collections by highlighting its role in preserving data security and supporting scholarly research. Jones and Lauriault (2017) discuss the challenges and strategies of managing access to digital geospatial data, underscoring the importance of access control in protecting sensitive geographic information. Stvilia et al. (2017) explore the impact of access policies on the usage and preservation of digital repositories, advocating for flexible access management frameworks that balance user accessibility with data protection. Furthermore, adherence to access control principles aligns with professional standards and best practices in library and information science, emphasising the ethical responsibility of libraries to manage and protect digital assets (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 2015; Association of College & Research Libraries, 2018). By implementing robust access control measures, academic libraries can ensure

compliance with legal mandates, safeguard intellectual property, and promote equitable access to scholarly resources.

The study underscores that user authentication plays a crucial role in the management of digital collections within academic libraries. User authentication refers to the process of verifying the identity of individuals accessing digital resources, typically through username-password combinations, biometric data, or other secure methods. This mechanism ensures that only authorised users can access and interact with sensitive or restricted digital materials, thereby safeguarding data integrity, protecting intellectual property, and maintaining user privacy. The rationale for this study outcome is rooted in the imperative to balance accessibility with security in digital library environments (Jeng & Hsia, 2018; McLeod & Jeng, 2020). Effective user authentication protocols enable research libraries to implement tailored access controls that align with legal requirements, institutional policies, and ethical standards, thereby mitigating risks associated with unauthorised access or data breaches.

Previous studies support the significance of user authentication in managing digital collections by highlighting its role in enhancing data security and supporting scholarly inquiry. Jeng and Hsia (2018) discuss the implementation of user authentication systems in digital libraries, emphasising their impact on user access management and content protection. McLeod and Jeng (2020) explore authentication strategies for preserving digital collections, advocating for robust authentication mechanisms to ensure data integrity and compliance with privacy regulations. Furthermore, adherence to user authentication principles aligns with professional guidelines and best practices in library and information science, emphasising the responsibility of libraries to safeguard digital assets and uphold user trust (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 2015; American Library Association, 2019). By implementing secure user authentication frameworks, research libraries can mitigate security risks, protect intellectual property rights, and promote responsible use of digital resources.

The study highlights the critical role of encryption in the management of digital collections within academic libraries. Encryption involves encoding digital

information to prevent unauthorized access, ensuring that data remains confidential and secure during storage, transmission, and access. In research library contexts, where sensitive scholarly and archival materials are stored and accessed, encryption serves as a foundational safeguard to protect intellectual property, uphold data integrity, and maintain user privacy. The rationale for this study outcome is grounded in the essential need for robust data protection mechanisms in digital library environments (Berti et al., 2019; Niu & Li, 2018). Encryption technologies provide a secure framework for storing and transmitting digital collections, mitigating risks associated with cyberattacks, data breaches, and unauthorised access.

Conclusion

This study highlighted the critical role of data integrity, access control, user authentication, and encryption in the effective management of digital collections in the University of Calabar and the University of Cross River State libraries. The findings underscore the importance of these factors in ensuring the reliability, security, and accessibility of digital resources. By maintaining high standards of data integrity, implementing robust access control mechanisms, ensuring secure user authentication processes, and employing advanced encryption techniques, academic libraries can enhance the management and protection of their digital collections. These measures not only safeguard the libraries' digital assets but also foster a trustworthy environment for users to access and utilize these resources effectively.

Recommendations

1. Academic libraries should adopt comprehensive data integrity protocols to ensure that digital collections remain accurate, consistent, and reliable. This can be achieved through regular data audits, use of checksums, and implementation of version control systems.
2. Libraries should implement multi-layered access control mechanisms to regulate who can view or modify digital collections. Role-based access

- control (RBAC) and least privilege principles should be applied to minimize unauthorized access and potential data breaches.
3. To safeguard digital collections, libraries should employ advanced user authentication methods such as multi-factor authentication (MFA), biometric verification, and single sign-on (SSO) solutions. These measures will help verify the identities of users and prevent unauthorized access.
 4. Libraries should utilize state-of-the-art encryption methods to protect digital collections from unauthorized access and cyber threats. End-to-end encryption and secure encryption key management practices should be employed to ensure data security both in transit and at rest.
 5. Ongoing training programs should be established to keep library staff updated on the latest security practices, potential threats, and the importance of maintaining data integrity, access control, user authentication, and encryption standards.

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